

Modeling and Control of an Interleaved Boost Converter for Fuel Cell Electric Vehicle Application: Addressing Minimum Phase Behavior

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Abstract: The application of high-gain DC-DC converters with minimum phase behaviour and low input current ripple in the field of low-voltage fuel cell power generation is becoming increasingly important. In this article, an interleaved boost converter (IBC) utilizing its inductive parts charge-discharge behaviour along with controlled switches switching operations for fuel cell-based EV applications is discussed. Further, due to these switching operations and charging-discharging behaviour, the right half-plane zero of the conventional dc-dc boost converter control-to-DC output voltage transfer function is nullified and the IBC becomes minimum phase system. Additionally, this IBC achieves reduced input current ripples and output voltage ripple also reduces the voltage and current stress on the semiconductor devices. Further, to achieve an efficient and stable power conversion, a simple and robust controller is implemented. A detailed analysis of system dynamics is conducted by deriving the open-loop transfer function, accounting the parasitic effects of the inductor and capacitor, and followed by the controller design. Moreover, the analysis includes, state-space averaging with small-signal modeling and transient response during sudden change in duty cycle/reference voltage to assess the IBC performance for FCEVs applications. Additionally, the efficiency comparison, has been conducted to Fig.-out the effectiveness of IBC. The proposed approach is validated through MATLAB Simulink, which confirm the IBC's superior steady-state and dynamic performance.

Keywords: Fuel cell, interleaved boost converter, minimum phase behavior, right half-plane zero, ripple current

Nomenclature

L_{m1}, L_{m2}	Inductors	$i_{L_{m1}}, i_{L_{m2}}$	Inductors current
I_{rms}	RMS current through Inductor	ΔV_o	Voltage ripple
$R_{L_{m1}}, R_{L_{m2}}$	Inductor resistance	$\Delta i_{L_{m1}}$	Current ripple of inductor L_{m1}
$R_{ds(on)}$	On-state resistance	f_{sw}	Switching frequency
$I_{sw(rms)}$	RMS current through MOSFET	V_g	Input voltage
$I_{D(avg)}$	Average current through diode	V_o	Output voltage
V_f	Forward voltage drop of diode	ΔI_o	Output current ripple
P_{out}	Output power	I_o	Output current
P_{Loss}	Total power loss of IBC	ΔI_{in}	Input current ripple
t_{on}, t_{off}	Turn-on and turn-off time of switches	I_{in}	Input current
R_{Co}	Capacitor resistance		

I. Introduction

Fuel Cell Electric Vehicles (FCEVs) are

increasingly seen as a promising option for eco-friendly transportation because of their numerous benefits, such as zero emissions, energy diversification, short refuelling time for long cruising range, and immense power supply for household or emergency use [1]-[3]. However, the voltage level of a Fuel Cell (FC) is typically less than 1.2 V [4]. Therefore, for achieving a high voltage level, multiple cells are stacked together in series to form a FC stack and the stack produces the required electrical energy to power the FCEVs [5]. However, for obtaining a stable voltage from 400 to 800 V in efficient manner to power the vehicle loads (motor and other accessories), a greater number of FC stacks are required which results increase in overall volume and cost [6]. To address this limitation, the conventional dc-dc boost converters are introduced to efficiently increase the FC voltage level to a desired voltage level. Meanwhile, the Conventional Boost Converters (CBCs) have an issue of non-minimum phase behaviour. This is a phenomenon that occurs due to the presence of right half plane zero in its control-to-DC output voltage transfer function. Due to the existence of non-minimum phase behaviour, nonlinear property during the dynamic conditions has been experienced [7]. Further, the gain margin and phase margin of the system varies reverse manner, which leads instability of the overall system [8]. Also, because of this non-minimum phase behaviour, the overshoot and undershoot natured output voltage would be observed during sudden decrease and increase in duty ratio or reference voltage [9]. Moreover, due to this non-minimum phase behaviour, the controller design becomes more complex [10]. Another drawback of CBC is that they are not suitable for handling high power. Further, it is quite complex for the CBC to handle high current and voltage ripple in the passive elements like inductor and capacitor, which leads to increase in losses and stress in the semiconductor devices [11]. In case of CBC, due to the

presence of single inductor high ripple current is observed for high power applications [12]. To address these issues in CBCs, several techniques have been introduced, including coupled inductors, isolated transformers, switched capacitors, capacitor-clamped H-type, switched inductors, and voltage doubler topologies. However, these topologies have complex structures, requiring various components, and the volume of the components is high [13]-[14]. Further, compared to isolated topologies, non-isolated topologies are more suited for applications that do not necessitate electrical isolation and owing to their superior power density.

Over the past decades, various dc-dc converter topologies have been introduced and among them Interleaved Boost Converters (IBCs) are very popular for their advantageous features like, decent voltage gain, suppressed current and voltage ripple, reduced voltage and current stress and improved efficiency [15]-[17]. The current stress on switching components and current ripple on inductive parts are reduced due to the current distribution between the different inductor legs. Reduced ripple leads to an increase the lifetime of FC, and output capacitor [18]-[21]. The interleaving approach improves power density, enhances dynamic response, and boosts conversion efficiency. In [22], the input current ripple suppression technique has been discussed by splitting input current across two phases with phase-shifted operations. IBC is derived from the CBC and inherits its non-minimum phase behaviour. However, a Right Half-Plane Zero (RHPZ) in its control-to-output transfer function causes an initial voltage dip when increasing the duty cycle and vice-versa. In [23], a magnetically coupled inductors-based boost converter with enhanced filter capacitor has been discussed to make the converter minimum phase. Similarly, a magnetically coupled filter inductors with a series RC damping network has been introduced to eliminate RHP zero and offers adequate phase margin

and optimum bandwidth for achieving a stable output during dynamic load variations [13]. Further, for maintaining a stable output voltage under different loading conditions required advanced control techniques like, phase-shading control [23], sliding mode control [24], fuzzy logic control [16], model predictive control [9], phase-shifting and active disturbance rejection technique [12], and dual control strategy [8] have been proposed to enhance voltage regulation and current balancing. Though these methods improve performance; however, it results the overall system design and the controller design becomes complex.

To address the issues like, drawbacks of non-minimum phase behaviour, high current and voltage ripple as well as stresses for high power applications, and low power density of CBC; in this article an interleaved boost converter for fuel cell based electric vehicle applications with simple controller design to ensure minimum phase behaviour, reduce current and voltage ripple as well as stress using fewer components is discussed. Interleaving minimises voltage and current ripple, decreases inductor size, which reduces the overall system size and cost. Further, the discussed design enhances the power capability, reliability, and transient response. Meanwhile, it requires a smaller filter compared to other boost-derived converter techniques to make it well-suited for FCEVs.

The contribution of this work can be as follows:

- A basic design of a controller is suggested to attain minimum phase behaviour in an IBC, which overcomes the disadvantages of a conventional boost converter.
- The converter exhibits a significant reduction in the current and voltage ripple that reduces the stress on the components and enhances efficiency.

- The design allows reduced inductor and filter size through the concept of interleaving, which allows better power density and results in a smaller system size, lower cost and weight.
- The given approach makes the improvements with lower components, which is a unique advantage of the proposed approach in comparison with current IBC implementations.
- It has an increased power capability, reliability and transient response, thus making it very favourable to the FCEV application.
- The design will need a smaller filter than other boost-derived topologies, such that a compact and low-cost solution is achieved that can be used in high-power clean mobility systems.

This paper is structured as, Section I provides an impactful introduction that includes a comprehensive literature survey. Section II describes the converter operation and presents the key waveforms of the IBC. Section III develops the state-space modelling and derives the transfer function of the IBC, which includes controller design, the design of passive components, and also the verification of the minimum phase behaviour of the IBC through pole-zero plots. Section IV presents the results and discussion, focusing on the dynamic response and ripple current in the input side of the IBC along with comparison of efficiency. Section V concludes the study and outlines future research opportunities.

II. Converter Operation and Waveform

Two dc-dc conventional boost converters are combinedly incorporated to form interleaved boost converter (IBC) and

it is shown in Fig. 1. The circuit consists of two controlled switches (Q_1, Q_2) that operates 180° out of phases, two diodes (D_1, D_2) operate contradict with their respectively branch controlled switches, two inductors (L_{m1}, L_{m2}), input voltage (V_g), output voltage (V_o), and output filter capacitance (C_o). The parasitic elements inductor resistances R_{Lm1}, R_{Lm2} , and capacitor resistance R_{Co} are considered during the operation of the IBC. The inductors currents i_{Lm1} and i_{Lm2} operates in continuous current mode to improve power density as compare to CBC. The circuit is operating in two modes, Mode I & II. The equivalent circuits for both modes are shown in Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 respectively. The state space equations are established according to the two possible switching modes, and the various operational key waveforms are shown in Fig. 4.

Fig. 1. Interleaved Boost Converter

Mode-I ($0 < t < t_1$): Starts when switch Q_1 is in ON position and Q_2 is in OFF position; and D_2 is forward-biased condition. The inductor current i_{Lm1} starts charging and stored energy for the next mode of operation, whereas the stored energy of L_{m2} along with some parts of input source passes through the diode D_2 to the load side.

Fig. 2. Equivalent circuit of IBC during Mode-I

Mode-II ($t_1 < t < t_2$): In this mode the controlled switch Q_1 is on turn OFF position and the switch Q_2 is on turn ON position. During this mode the inductor current i_{Lm2} starts charging and stores energy in it, whereas the stored energy of L_{m1} starts discharging along with some parts of source voltage through the diode D_1 to the load end.

Fig. 3. Equivalent circuit of IBC during Mode-II

From the various operational key waveforms shown in Fig. 4, it is observed that the switches Q_1 and Q_2 are operating in complementary manner. During the ON state of each switch, the corresponding inductor coil is in charging mode and stores energy. In contrast, the current through the other inductor coil starts discharging the stored energy along with the voltage source to the load. As both the coils are charging and discharging in complementary manner, the input current ripple is reduced as compared to the CBC.

Because the input current is the combined result of both the individual inductor currents. Further, due to this phase shifting behaviour of controlled switches and charging-discharging characteristics of inductor coils, the output voltage ripple is also suppressed. Additionally, from the operational key waveforms the voltage across both the diodes D_1 and D_2 are observed and it is noticed that each of the diode is in forward biased conditions in complementary manner with the respective branch-controlled switches. Duty cycle plays a critical role in determining the ON state duration of each switch, enabling efficient energy transfer to the load.

Fig. 4. Operational waveform

III. State Space Modelling and Transfer Function

The state-space model is established by considering the operating states of all the controlled switches present in the IBC. As two controlled switches, Q1 and Q2, operate in a complementary manner, for the state space modelling, two operating states are considered. Here, the inductor current i_{Lm1} , i_{Lm2} , and the capacitor voltage C_0 are chosen as the state variables. Also, the equivalent series resistance for each inductive and capacitive element has been considered.

i. When Q_1 is ON and Q_2 is OFF

The equations under this mode can be represented as

$$\dot{x} = [A_1]x + [B_1]u \text{ and } y = [C_1]x + [D_1]u$$

$$\begin{cases} L_{m1} \frac{di_{Lm1}}{dt} = V_g - R_{Lm1} \\ L_{m2} \frac{di_{Lm2}}{dt} = V_g - R_{Lm2} - V_0 \\ C_0 \frac{dv_{C_0}}{dt} = i_{Lm2} - \frac{V_0}{R} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

$$A_1 = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{R_{Lm1}}{L_{m1}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{R_{Lm2} + \frac{R \times R_{C_0}}{R + R_{C_0}}}{L_{m2}} & -\frac{R}{(R + R_{C_0})} \\ 0 & \frac{R}{C_0(R + R_{C_0})} & -\frac{R}{C_0(R + R_{C_0})} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$B_1 = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{L_{m1}} & 0 & 0 \\ \frac{1}{L_{m2}} & 0 & -\frac{1}{L_{m2}} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad C_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{R_{C_0}}{R + R_{C_0}} & \frac{R}{R + R_{C_0}} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$D_1 = [0]$$

ii. When Q_1 is OFF and Q_2 is ON
The equations under this mode can be represented as

$$\dot{x} = [A_2]x + [B_2]u \text{ and } y = [C_2]x + [D_2]u$$

$$\begin{cases} L_{m1} \frac{di_{Lm1}}{dt} = V_g - R_{Lm1} - V_0 \\ L_{m2} \frac{di_{Lm2}}{dt} = V_g - R_{Lm2} \\ C_0 \frac{dv_{C_0}}{dt} = i_{Lm1} - \frac{V_0}{R} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

$$A_2 = \begin{bmatrix} -\frac{R_{Lm1}}{L_{m1}} \left(\frac{R \times R_{C_0}}{R + R_{C_0}} + 1 \right) & 0 & -\frac{R}{L_{m1}(R + R_{C_0})} \\ 0 & \frac{-R_{Lm2}}{L_{m2}} & 0 \\ \frac{R}{C_0(R + R_{C_0})} & 0 & -\frac{1}{C_0(R + R_{C_0})} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$B_2 = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{L_{m1}} & -\frac{1}{L_{m1}} & 0 \\ \frac{1}{L_{m2}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad C_2 = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{R_{C_0}}{R + R_{C_0}} & 0 & \frac{R}{R + R_{C_0}} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$D_2 = [0]$$

by applying Volt – Sec and charge-sec balance from (1) and (2)

$$V_0 = \frac{V_g}{(1 - D)} \quad (3)$$

$$i_{Lm} = \frac{V_g}{(1 - D)^2 \times R} \quad (4)$$

From the state equation, the derived state transfer function is as follows:

$$M \frac{du}{dt} = [(A_1D + A_2(1 - D)U] + [(B_1D + B_2(1 - D)U_0] \quad (5)$$

Steady-state model is derived when all perturbations are set to zero.

$$U = -A^{-1}BU_0 \quad (6)$$

M is the state variable matrix (inductor currents and capacitor voltage), M is the coefficient matrix, and D and (1-D) denote the ON and OFF duty cycles, respectively.

$$M_1 = \begin{bmatrix} L_{m1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & L_{m2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & C_0 \end{bmatrix}, M_2 = \begin{bmatrix} L_{m1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & L_{m2} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & C_0 \end{bmatrix}$$

where M_1 and M_2 are the coefficient matrix during ON and OFF states, respectively,

$M = [M_1D + M_2(1 - D)]$, $A = [A_1D + A_2(1 - D)]$, $B = [B_1D + B_2(1 - D)]$, $C = [C_1D + C_2(1 - D)]$ and also the matrices U and U_0 are as follows:

$$U = \begin{bmatrix} iL_{m1} \\ iL_{m2} \\ V_{C_0} \end{bmatrix}, U_0 = \begin{bmatrix} V_g \\ D \end{bmatrix}$$

hence, the small signal transfer function of the state variable for the IBC is given as

$$T.F = (C \times [SI - A]^{-1}B + D) \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{\tilde{V}_0(s)}{\tilde{d}(s)} = \frac{a_2S^2 + a_1S^1 + a_0}{b_3S^3 + b_2S^2 + b_1S^1 + b_0} \quad (8)$$

Where a_2, a_1, a_0 and b_3, b_2, b_1, b_0 are the numerator and denominator coefficients of the transfer function.

Fig. 5. Bode Plot of IBC (compensated and uncompensated system)

3.1 Comparison of Compensated and Uncompensated Plot of IBC

The discussed interleaved boost converter is a boost modified type converter, the PI and PID controller do not exhibit better dynamic performance with load change condition and parametric uncertainty. Further, from [24], it may be observed that the optimized type-II controllers exhibit better dynamic performance, decent bandwidth and larger margin of stability. So, a type-II controller is used to get adequate gain margin and phase margin. The type-II controller is one kind of lead type controller with a pole at the origin. Hence, it provides a maximum 90° phase boost with zero steady-state error. Moreover, this Type-II controller exhibits better transient performance when this converter is tuned properly. In contrast, using this type-II controller the GM and PM of compensated one is 11.9 dB and 45.3°. In Fig. 5, the bode plot of compensated and uncompensated IBC systems are shown and analyze the stability. The bode plot depicts the frequency response of a control system of compensated and uncompensated systems. In contrast, the compensated system shows improved gain across a broader frequency range, enhancing system response and stability. The compensation effectively shifts the system's crossover frequency, demonstrating better dynamic performance and ensuring robust control under varying operating conditions.

3.2. Design of Passive Components

Passive elements are designed for the operation of IBC in continuous current mode (CCM). Inductor coils charging and discharging behaviour can be observed by considering some ripple percentage for input inductor currents iL_{m1} and iL_{m2} . The ripple in the input current ($\% \Delta I_{in}$) can be calculated by considering the waveform shown in Fig. 6. From the Fig. it can be noticed that during (DT_s) inductor L_{m1} is charging and $(1-D) T_s$ inductor L_{m1} is

discharging. The current ripple for both the coils are assumed to be less than 8 % ($\Delta i_{L_{m1}}$ and $\Delta i_{L_{m2}} \leq 8\%$). Similarly, for the capacitor ripple voltage is assumed to be less than 5 % ($\Delta V_0 \leq 5\%$).

Fig. 6. Input inductor L_{m1} current ripple

$$L_{m1} \geq \frac{V_g \times D}{\Delta i_{L_{m1}} \times f_{sw}} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{Similarly, } L_{m2} \geq \frac{V_g \times (1-D)}{\Delta i_{L_{m2}} \times f_{sw}} \quad (10)$$

As the input current I_{in} is the combination of both the inductor coil current and both the coils are charging and discharging alternatively, the input ripple current is reduced.

Sum of both inductors is equal to the total input current

$$i_{Lm} = i_{L_{m1}} + i_{L_{m2}} \quad (11)$$

Total inductor is considered as sum of individual inductors.

$$L_{m1} + L_{m2} = L_m \quad (12)$$

However, the output capacitor is calculated as

$$C_0 \geq \frac{D \times I_{in} \times V_g}{(1-D)^2 \times \Delta V_0 \times N \times f_{sw}} \quad (13)$$

3.3. Verification of Minimum phase behaviour of IBC

The proposed IBC shows minimum phase behavior, which is validated through

simulated results and P-Z plot for control to output transfer function $\tilde{V}_0(s)/\tilde{d}(s)$ of the IBC on chosen parameters. The P-Z plot shown in Fig. 7-Fig. 9 confirms that all zero-poles exist in the left-half plane of the complex plane for all duty cycles. Hence, it confirms that the IBC is showing minimum phase behaviour.

i. $D < 0.5$

The pole and zeros are positioned on the left-hand plane of complex plane as shown in Fig. 7, indicating a minimum-phase system. This configuration implies that the converter operates with favorable dynamics, avoiding instability-related issues. The zoomed versions show that the zeros are sufficiently distanced from the imaginary axis, ensuring minimal influence on the phase margin and aiding in smooth control response.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 7. P-Z plot of control-to-output transfer function (a) when $D < 0.5$, (b) Zoomed view of (a) indicating all P-Z Lies on LHP

ii. $D = 0.5$

The pole and zeros positions are also within the left-hand plane of the complex plane as shown in Fig. 8, maintaining the system's stability. The system's response might exhibit a slightly faster response than at $D < 0.5$, as poles tend to move closer to the imaginary axis with increasing duty cycle. The zoomed-in plots reveal the fine positioning of zeros, confirming the absence of RHPZ and supporting robust control characteristics.

Fig. 8. P-Z plot of control-to-output transfer function (a) when $D = 0.5$, (b) Zoomed view of (a) indicating all P-Z Lies on the LHP

iii. $D > 0.5$

The pole and zeros still reside within the complex plane's left-hand plane for higher duty cycle, as shown in Fig. 9, affirming the converter's stable behaviour across a wider duty cycle range. However, the proximity of poles to the imaginary axis suggests an even faster dynamic response, which might enhance transient performance. The

zoomed plots highlight that, even at this high-duty cycle, the system avoids RHPZ, reinforcing its minimum-phase nature and ensuring controllability and stability.

Fig. 9. P-Z plot of control-to-output transfer function (a) when $D > 0.5$, (b) Zoomed view of (a) indicating all P-Z Lies on LHP

The pole and zero analysis evaluated system stability across different duty ranges. Results showed that P-Z lies on the left-hand side of the complex plane, indicating stable operation across all D . This underscores the system's robustness and reliability, validating the converter's design for consistent stability in practical applications. The D significantly influences the IBC's dynamic performance, affecting gain, phase margin, and control stability. Thus, assessing stability across all duty cycle was essential. The observed stability ensures reliable operation in scenarios like load variations, making the system suitable for applications such as FCEVs.

IV. Results and Discussion

The simulation of the IBC with a Type-II controller was performed using MATLAB SIMULINK (2023a). The analysis was conducted in both the frequency and time domains to evaluate the converter's performance. The frequency response of the IBC was verified using Bode plots, which illustrate both uncompensated and compensated system responses. This comparison highlights the effectiveness of the Type-II controller in enhancing system stability and dynamic performance. The presence of the RHPZ was examined through P-Z analysis. The results confirm that the IBC exhibits minimum phase characteristics, ensuring a stable and well-controlled output without the instability issues typically associated with CBC. The dynamic response of the IBC was analysed. Fig. 10 presents the input current, which remains steady at 66.66 A, while Fig. 11 shows the output current of 24.66 A. Fig. 12 illustrates the inductor-balanced currents, demonstrating effective current sharing between the two inductors. The output voltage, well-regulated at 400 V, is shown in Fig. 13. Further evaluating the converter's performance under transient conditions, Fig. 14 shows the output voltage waveform during a sudden step change, confirming the absence of overshoot and undershoot, highlighting the system's robustness. Additionally, the dynamic characteristics of voltage control in the IBC, where step-up from 400V to 500V and step-down from 500V to 400V can be observed. Fig. 15 shows a zoomed view of the step-up transition in voltage and duty ratio occurring at 4.244 seconds, while Fig. 16 presents the zoomed view of the step-down transition at 5.35 seconds. These results show the transitions change, offering a detailed perspective on the converter's stability and smooth voltage regulation. Unlike non-minimum phase boost-derived dc-dc converters, these voltage responses confirm the absence of RHPZs in the IBC, as no transient overshoots or undershoots

occur during abrupt changes in load current and duty ratio. The design parameter of IBC is presented in Table 1.

Table 1- Converter Parameters

Parameters	Value
Supply voltage (V_g)	150 V
Output Voltage (V_o)	400 V
Inductor (L_{m1}, L_{m2})	735 mH
Switching Frequency (f_{sw})	20 kHz
Filter Capacitor (C_o)	0.117 μ F
Duty Cycle (D)	0.63
Power rating (P)	10 kW

Fig. 10. Input current (I_{in}) waveform of IBC

Fig. 11. Output current (I_o) of IBC

Fig. 12. Both Inductor current (i_{Lm1} and i_{Lm2}) of IBC

Fig. 13. Output voltage of IBC

(a)

(b)

Fig. 14. Output voltage of IBC with no voltage dip during step change (a) step up change (b) step down change

(a)

(b)

Fig. 15. Zoomed view of output voltage of IBC during step-up in duty ratio (a) step-up in voltage (b) step-down in duty ratio

(a)

(b)

Fig. 16. Zoomed view of output voltage of IBC during step-down in duty ratio (a) step-down in voltage (b) step-down in duty ratio

4.1 Ripple Analysis

This interleaved operation minimizes current ripple, voltage ripple, reduces losses, lowers stress and enhances performance in high-power and high-efficiency applications. The advantage of IBC is having a low ripple in input and output current. This can be verified through Simulation results, which show the input and output ripple current and output voltage ripple of IBC at different duty cycles as

shown in Fig. 17 – Fig. 19. When $D=0.5$, perfect ripple cancellation is observed, confirming the effective phase interleaving, and for $D>0.5$ and $D<0.5$, partial ripple cancellation occurs.

Fig. 17. Input current ripple

Fig. 18. Output current ripple

Fig. 19. Output voltage ripple

The input current ripple is less at the low duty cycle and higher for the higher duty cycle, and at $D=0.5$ it is negligible, as shown in Fig. 20 – Fig. 22, and also the same for the output current ripple, as shown in Fig. 23 - Fig. 25.

Fig. 20. Input current ripple of IBC at $D = 0.4$

Fig. 21. Input current ripple of IBC at $D = 0.5$

Fig. 22. Input current ripple of IBC at $D = 0.7$

Fig. 23. Output current of IBC ripple at $D = 0.4$

Fig. 24. Output current ripple of IBC at $D = 0.5$

Fig. 25. Output current ripple of IBC at $D = 0.7$

The total current is divided into two paths, and it is verified that the inductor current ripple is higher than the input and output ripple current. Since the current is splitting, the losses are reduced, and the stress of each device can be minimized. The output voltage has a low voltage ripple, shown in Fig. 26 – Fig. 28, which shows that when the duty increases, the output voltage ripple increases and at $D=0.5$, a negligible ripple can be seen.

Fig. 26. Output voltage ripple of IBC at $D = 0.4$

Fig. 27. Output voltage of IBC at $D=0.5$

Fig. 28. Output voltage of IBC at $D=0.7$

4.2 Efficiency

An efficiency comparison graph, as shown in Fig. 29, shows that IBC has superior efficiency compared to CBC [8] and Multidevice Boost Converter Topology (MDBC) [21]. As ripple reduction leads to lower power losses in

key passive components, such as inductors and capacitors. As a result, the IBC not only achieves better energy conversion efficiency but also improves overall reliability and performance, particularly in high-power applications.

Fig. 29. Efficiency analysis of converters at different loading conditions

CBC, IBC, and MDBC are compared with the same power rating. The comparison highlights that the proposed IBC achieves the highest efficiency (97.58%) with fewer components than the MDBC, which, despite having additional switches and diodes, has a lower efficiency (95.32%). With its simplest structure, the CBC has the lowest efficiency (93.74%) due to higher ripple and losses. The interleaved design in the IBC improves performance by reducing current ripple and enhancing power conversion efficiency while maintaining a relatively simple structure compared to the MDBC, making it a more efficient choice for high-power applications.

V. Conclusion

This paper demonstrates the significant benefits of the modified IBC for FCEV applications. The small signal transfer function and average state space for voltage control regulation were derived. By eliminating the RHPZ, the proposed IBC achieves minimum phase behavior. The IBC effectively reduces input current ripple, output voltage ripple, and the size of

passive elements. The closed-loop control scheme further enhances the converter's efficiency and performance. MATLAB simulations validate the steady-state performance and advantages of the proposed IBC design, highlighting its potential for future applications in FCEVs. This research provides a solid foundation for further advancements in power conversion technology for electric vehicles, addressing various key challenges and proposing innovative solutions for improved power management.

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